

VOCABULARY ENHANCEMENT SYSTEM BASED ON THE METHODOLOGY OF TOURISM TERMINOLOGY

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Annotation

The article deals with the classification of legal terms in English and Uzbek languages offered by linguists. The author discusses corresponding criteria for legal terms in the conception of lawyers and linguists.

Keywords

English tourism terms and terminology, classification of terms, terminology, terminology system, comparative analysis.

Language is the main means of preserving and enriching our spiritual heritage. The history, development, and future of each industry or event are certainly closely related to the language. (Matthew 24:14; 28:19, 20) Today, among other areas of linguistics, terminology plays an important role in the development of linguistics. Over the years, the number of theoretical and practical terms in this area has increased. The initial motivation for the study of terminology was as theoretical as the motive for the emergence of science and the origin of science. As a result of the significant development of technology and communications during this period of growth, terminology has been regarded as a necessary tool to overcome some of the challenges associated with many developments.

Only in the 20th century terminology acquired a scientific direction, and at the same time was recognized as an activity of social importance. Today's modern tourism includes extreme, exotic, gastronomic and spectacular types. Gastronomic tours are organized for those who want a bright and sweet taste and those interested in the field of cooking. Of course, the uniqueness of each country is reflected through its national hotel. American scientists B. Joseph Payne II and James Gilmore, in their study of impressions as a fourth economic proposition, concluded that "the economy of impressions has its own characteristics. When a person buys an impression, he pays for his feelings and emotions. Gastro-tours are organized to present such impressions to people. The purpose of this is to get

acquainted with the local cuisine and traditions of national dishes of different countries, as well as to taste exotic and special tastes. The difference between gastronomic tourism and ordinary tourism is that in gastronomic tourism, tourists get to know the special taste of food and the traditions of food preparation.

The term gastronomic tourism is interpreted differently in special literature: "culinary tourism", "food tourism" - "food tourism", "gastronomic tourism" - "gastronomic tourism". The term "culinary tourism" was coined for the first time in 1998 by L. Long, who put into circulation the idea that "people understand other cultures through their local foods." Eric Wolf, Head of the International Food Tourism Organization, said, "Gastronomic tourism is the search for and enjoyment of distinctive, unforgettable, unique foods and beverages around the world. It is not necessary to travel the whole world in search of an exotic taste, you can organize a gastronomic tour in your own city. One can also travel around one's hometown. The distance we cover is not as important as the fact that we are constantly moving. Thus, we are all "travelers" and "eaters", we can even consider ourselves gastronomic tourists.

Tourism terminology is one of the systems of terms that have been developing rapidly in recent years. A term is a lexical unit of a certain language intended for a certain purpose, that defines a general - specific or abstract - theory of a certain knowledge or activity. First of all, if we look at the history of the term "tourism", this term appeared not only to satisfy human needs, but also to understand the possibility of recreation. The tourism sector is undoubtedly one of the leading factors of socio-economic development of every country. It is no exaggeration to say that the demand for this field is increasing year by year.

The word "tourism" was borrowed from the French language in the 19th century and gives the meaning of a special leisure activity in a narrow sense, but the broad meaning is to know the world, to strive for a healthy lifestyle, to get new emotions. The origin of the word is related to the French word "tourisme", which is derived from the root "tour" - travel, walk. The main meaning of the word was used until the 19th century - circle, rotation. It is also necessary to take measures to attract the segment of tourists who refuse the services of tour operators, that is, to open tourism offices of Uzbekistan in the main places that attract tourists, to attract the independent organized segment of tourists to our country, to organize gastronomic tourism. In our opinion, independent organized tourists have the characteristic of participating in activities related to gastronomic tourism.

English terms related to the food industry include single words and special phrases. The formation and development of English tourist terms according to our

analysis of scientific literature on tourism (Makarenko, Zorin) divided the history of English tourism into four stages corresponding to the stages of formation of English terminology. The division into these periods is based on the economic and social foundations, conditions and objectives of tourism that can be implemented at different stages of development.

The first stage - the "prototype of tourist activity" - covers the period from antiquity to the end of the 19th century, during which the main reasons for the British to travel were trade, medicine and, to a lesser extent, education. In the 21st century, the Grand Tour became popular in England, which means "the tour of rich people around the European continent." At this stage, only 6% of tourism terms currently studied in English were formed. Medical tourism The popularity of the Grand Tour has led to the emergence of tourism terms in English that refer to means of transportation and accommodation: resort, route, hotel, coach, excursion, board, etc. In this case, the nominations giving these lexical units are taken from the literary language. For example, in the common literary language, the word resort meant "something to seek help or help", and later it became a term with the meaning "a place where people go to relax".

Speaking about the first stage, it should be noted that this stage was not important in the development of tourism and tourism terminology on a large scale.

The second stage - "the beginning of the development of mass tourism" covers the entire XIX century, and at this stage, the methods of tourism management, the material and technical base began to appear, and, of course, the system of terms was further improved.

It was at this stage that the terms "tourism" and "tourist" were formed. Nowadays, it is natural for cultural words to be used internationally and to enter our language and become popular. The words "restaurant", "coffee shop" in Uzbek are now used as "restaurant" and "cafe" under the influence of linguistic and cultural globalization. In addition, the word "menu" in the field of restaurant and cafe service is also used now.

It is in the works dedicated to the research of terms related to tourism that the lexicographic interpretation of terms, their translation and cross-linguistic comparison are devoted, and are notable for their scientific and practical importance. In the years of independence, great attention was paid to the development of tourism, not only to the development of the tourism sector, but also to the implementation of projects and scientific research aimed at solving linguistic and lexicographical problems related to this sector, and led to a more in-depth study of terms related to tourism.

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